

**EFFECT OF THERMAL SHRINKAGE TO THE REINFORCEMENT CARBON FIBER
IN THE CARBON CARBON COMPOSITE DURING CARBONIZATION PROCESS**

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ABSTRACT

Interaction between the thermal shrinkage of carbon carbon composite during carbonization process and the orientation of crystallites in carbon fiber as reinforcement of the composite was studied by comparing the crystallite size both the carbon fiber heat-treated in a free state and the fiber in composite.

The carbon fiber in composite indicated more preferred orientation for crystallite than the carbon fiber heat treated in a free state, which was examined by TEM analysis.

Therefore, it was assumed that the stress caused by thermal shrinkage in the perpendicular direction effected to the orientation for crystallite of carbon fibers in the composite.

Key words : Carbon carbon composite, Thermal shrinkage, TEM,
Carbonization process.

1. INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced carbon composites show interesting many kinds of properties, which is well known. The properties of carbon carbon composite mainly depend on the raw materials.

Pitch based carbon carbon composites indicate high strength high modulus properties(1). Especially, Young's modulus may be far away from the estimated Young's modulus by a simple rule of mixture. Such as this phenomena might be generally concluded with the contribution of well oriented carbonized matrices (2,3), or with the increasing for Young's modulus of carbon fiber itself according to increasing heat treatment temperature(1). In any way, the elastic properties of the composite could be related to the degree of preferred orientation in the carbon fiber and carbon matrix.

In this study, it is hypothesized that thermal expansion behavior of carbon carbon composite during the fabricating carbonization procedure may effect to the carbon fiber as reinforcement in terms of the crystallite orientation in carbon fiber. For this reason, this investigation was undertaken by comparing

the crystallite size both the carbon fiber heat-treated in a free state and the carbon fiber heat-treated in carbon carbon composite.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Materials used

This study was performed with unidirectionally reinforced carbon carbon composites. This composite consists of slightly carbonized mesophase pitch based fibers (CARBONIC HM20 : PETOCA Ltd.) and petroleum derived pitch carbon. This composite was prepared by resin-char method with multiple-densification technique. The composite as samples was heat-treated up to 650°C in order to investigate its thermal expansion behavior during carbonization process up to 2000°C (in situ).

2.2 Measurement of Thermal Expansion Behavior

Thermal expansion behavior, both carbon fibers as reinforcement materials and the carbon carbon composite, was measured up to 2000°C (in situ) with heating rate 15°C/minute in Argon gas atmosphere by high temperature thermal mechanical analyzer (SETARAM DHT 2400K Thermo Mechanical Analyzer System).

2.3 TEM Analysis

After measurement of thermal expansion behavior, both the carbon fiber and the composite were analysed by TEM analysis technique. TEM analysis operated at 300kV was performed for both carbon fibers in the parallel direction to fiber axis. TEM image and selected area electron diffraction (SAED) pattern was taken for each carbon fibers.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3-1. Thermal expansion behavior of carbon fiber HM20

Displacement and thermal expansion coefficient (TEC) curves are shown in Figure 1. Since this carbon fiber is heat-treated at low temperature which correspond to the transitional point (about 1250°C) in TEC curve, this carbon fiber shows an extreme thermal expansion above original heat treatment temperature up to 2000°C.

Figure 1. Thermal expansion behavior of the carbon fiber HM20.
(DISPL: ———, TEC: - - -)

3-2. Thermal expansion behavior of the carbon carbon composite

Displacement and TEC curves are shown in Figure 2. In a parallel direction, thermal expansion behavior of the composite precursor which was consisted of HM20 and pitch carbon, was almost the same patterns such as the curves of the carbon fiber HM20 except the behavior at near 800°C. But the total displacement was smaller than that of carbon fiber.

In a perpendicular direction to fiber axis, displacement and TEC curves are shown in Figure 3. the composite showed an extreme shrinkage (4.05 %) during heat treatment up to 2000°C. Displacement curve indicated 2 steps shrinkage. The 2 steps shrinkage was detected obviously in the TEC curve. That first shrinkage at near 800°C correspond to the shrinkage observed at the same temperature in the parallel direction. The first shrinkage might start from 650°C (original heat treatment temperature). Because an extreme change was detected in TEC curve at near 650°C. Since such a shrinkage was not observed in the case of carbon fiber HM20, this shrinkage should depend on the characteristic of the matrix on the way of heat treatment. And the subsequent thermal shrinkage behavior in the temperature range higher than about 1200°C up to 2000°C, which may correspond to the thermal expansion in the parallel direction in the same temperature range above 1200°C. These thermal expansion behavior in the temperature range higher than about 1200°C, may depend on the characteristic both the carbon fiber HM20 and the pitch carbon matrix.

The carbon fiber HM20 become high strength high modulus carbon fiber, after heat treatment at high temperature above original heat treatment temperature. Therefore, in the temperature range higher than 1250°C, the orientation of crystallites in the carbon fiber should be further improved in the subsequent carbonization or graphitization process. Such the improvement of crystallite orientation occurs even in the carbon fiber itself.

In the case of the carbon carbon composite reinforced by HM20, the composite in a parallel direction showed almost the same thermal expansion behavior of the carbon fiber HM20 during heat treatment up to 2000°C. And this composite in a vertical direction showed an extreme shrinkage in the same temperature range. Consequently, the carbon fiber in carbon carbon composite may be carbonized under the stress caused by the thermal shrinkage during heat treatment procedure.

The stress may act on the surface of carbon fiber.

For this reason, the crystallite orientation of carbon fiber in the composite was compared with that of carbon fiber heat-treated alone in a free state.

3-3. TEM analysis

The TEM image and the SAED pattern of the carbon fiber heat-treated in the composite are shown in Figure 4 and 5, respectively. Those of the carbon fiber heat-treated in a free state are shown in Figure 6 and 7, respectively. In both TEM images, the (002) lattice fringes were observed on everywhere in the field of view. But the lattice fringes of the carbon fiber in composite were observed more clearly than those of the carbon fiber heat-treated in a free state. Furthermore, the SAED patterns indicated the same tendency, the (002) diffraction arcs for the carbon fiber in composite were observed more sharply than those for the carbon fiber heat-treated in a free state. The crystallite size (L_c) of carbon fiber in the composite was calculated as 13.0 nm, and the L_c of carbon fiber heat-treated in a free state was calculated as 7.7 nm.

As a result, the crystallite orientation in carbon fibers heat-treated in the composite were higher than that of carbon fibers heat-treated in a free state.

Consequently, it is suggested that the stress, induced by thermal shrinkage in a vertical direction to fiber axis during carbonization process, influence the improvement for crystallite orientation of carbon fiber in carbon carbon composite.

Figure 2. Thermal expansion behavior of the carbon carbon composite heat treated at 650°C (in a parallel direction to fiber axis during carbonization up to 2000°C).
 (DISPL: ———, TEC: - - - -)

Figure 3. Thermal expansion behavior of the carbon carbon composite heat treated at 650°C (in a vertical direction to fiber axis during carbonization up to 2000°C).
 (DISPL: ———, TEC: - - - -)

Figure 4. TEM image of the carbon fiber heat-treated up to 2000° C in the carbon/carbon composite.

Figure 6. TEM image of the carbon fiber heat-treated up to 2000° C in a free state.

Figure 5. SAED pattern of the carbon fiber heat-treated up to 2000°C in the carbon/carbon composite.

Figure 7. SAED pattern of the carbon fiber heat-treated up to 2000°C in a free state.

CONCLUSION

Interaction between the thermal shrinkage of carbon carbon composite during carbonization process and the orientation of crystallites in carbon fiber as reinforcement of the composite was investigated by TEM analysis techniques.

TEM image and SAED pattern showed that the crystallite orientation for the carbon fiber heat-treated in the composite was higher than that for the carbon fiber heat-treated in a free state.

Therefore, it is assumed that the stress caused by thermal shrinkage during carbonization process acts on the carbon fiber surface, and improve the orientation of crystallites in carbon fiber as reinforcement material of the carbon carbon composite.

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FIBRES
